

PERIODONTIC DISEASES AGAINST THE BACKGROUND OF TUBERCULOSIS IN CHILDREN AND ADOLESCENTS: FEATURES OF THE COURSE

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The purpose of this work is to assess the condition of periodontal tissues in children and adolescents infected with *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* and patients with tuberculosis (TB).

Materials and methods. A comprehensive dental examination of 215 children aged 6 to 17 years was carried out, including 63 children and adolescents with TB (1st group), 97 infected children (2nd group), and 55 healthy children (3rd group). The epidemiological, clinical, immunological, and microbiological features of periodontal disease were studied in all groups.

Results. The prevalence of periodontal diseases was significantly higher in patients of the 1st (88%) and the 2nd group (80%) against (41.8%) in the 3rd group. The most common pathology was catarrhal gingivitis – 74% in the 1st, 70% in the 2nd against 38.18% in the 3rd group. Periodontitis was diagnosed in 13% of patients in the 1st, 10% – the 2nd against 3.64% in the 3rd group. Catarrhal gingivitis in the 1st group had a chronic course (80%), in the 2nd – 60% against – 52% in the 3rd group. The acute course was most pronounced in the 1st group – 23% against 17% in the 2nd and 10% – in the 3rd group. In all age categories of patients of the 1st group, the PMA index was higher in relation to the 2nd group – from 52% in 9-11-year olds to 75% in 15-17-year-olds against 48-69% among children of the 2nd group. The prevalence of chronic catarrhal gingivitis and periodontitis increased depending on the severity of the clinical course of TB – from 71% in the 2nd group to 75% in the 1st group, catarrhal gingivitis had a chronic course and was defined as an average in 57%, its exacerbation was most often diagnosed in 27.5% patients of the 1st group and 19.1% patients of the 2nd group against 13.3% patients of the 3rd group. One-third of the respondents had an unsatisfactory state of oral hygiene, the Fedorov-Volodkina index ranged from 3.15 points in 6-8-year-olds to 2.35 points in 15-17-year-olds compared to 3.12 points in 6-8-year-olds to 2.3 points in 15-17-year-olds. Against the background of secondary immunodeficiency, the state of local immunity of the oral cavity was characterized by IL-1 β increase of the oral fluid in the 1st and the 2nd groups – 160 pg/ml and 140 pg/ml. sIgA was higher in the 1st group – 0.490 g/l against 0.345 g/l in the 2nd group. Lysozyme in both groups decreased with age. Associations of *Str. mutans* and *Lactobacillus* (65.0%) were most common on the surface of the gums in the 1st group versus 50% in the 2nd group; bacteria of the genus *Staphylococcus*

and *Lactobacillus* – 40% vs. 33%, bacteria of the genus *Streptococcus* and fungi of the genus *Candida* – 30% vs. 26.7%. A similar pattern was observed in oral fluid.

Conclusions. The prevalence of periodontal pathology in children and adolescents with tuberculosis depended on age, clinical form, and duration of TB disease. The largest number of children with an unsatisfactory and very poor level of oral hygiene was observed at the age of 6-8 years, in 15-17-year-olds, the share with satisfactory and unsatisfactory conditions prevailed. Impaired secretory immunity of the oral cavity and decreased lysozyme becomes the background against which the clinical manifestations of dental diseases are formed.